

Biota of Japanese Myxomycetes (Book Review)

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Japan is one of the most fascinating places in the world for myxomycetologists. Despite the small size of the country, Japan has four distinct seasons with a range in climate from the subarctic to the subtropics. Such environments have created diverse habitats that support a rich diversity of myxomycetes (see Fig. 1). We can hardly discuss this diversity without Yukinori Yamamoto's tremendous work (1135 pages!), which was published in 2021 by the Committee for the publication of *Biota of Japanese Myxomycetes*. The cost of the book is ¥12100 (ca \$110), and it is listed as ISBN: 978-4-600-00729-4.

Yukinori Yamamoto first published a monograph on Japanese myxomycetes in 1998. Since then, the number of records of Japanese species has increased, and vast changes have been proposed for the classification of the myxomycetes. In the current work, he basically followed the most recent systems of classification as proposed by Leontyev et al. (2019) and Wijayawardene (2020). He mentioned that the classification used for myxomycetes is still in development, and his hope for the future research is for the development of a natural system for the myxomycetes. In order to improve the convenience of identification, he also adopted several subgenera proposed by Nannenga-Bremekamp as "Form-subgenera."

This new book compiles the records of all of the species collected in Japan to date. As with all publications by Yukinori, this book has precise illustrations. Most importantly, he searched and examined all of the species recorded in Japan. The species for which he could not locate Japanese specimens were illustrated using exsiccatae from all over the world, and the locality and collectors of the specimens are also specified. In total, this book considers 514 species, 1 subspecies, 77 varieties and 14 forms as Japanese myxomycetes.

Although this book was written in Japanese, the species names, their synonyms, the first appearance as a written reference of each species in Japan, and the locality and collectors of the illustrated specimens were written in Roman letters. With his accurate illustrations, the information should be useful for anyone interested in these unique organisms. I highly recommend "*Biota of Japanese Myxomycetes*" to any myxomycetologist.

Figure 1. The genera *Lamproderma* (top) and *Cribraria* (bottom) are common in Japan and a complete discussion on the occurrence in this country is included in the book “Biota of Japanese Myxomycetes”. Illustrative images provided by Randy G. Darrah.